

Polarographic Behaviour of Pb(II) in Thiosulphate and Thiosulphate-Ethanol Media

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Formation constants of Pb(II)-thiosulphate complexes have been determined by polarography. The maximum coordination number is 2 or 3, depending on the concentration of thiosulphate, ionic strength and the ethanol content. It has been shown that the complexes are more stable at higher percentage of alcohol and less so at higher ionic strength. They are reduced reversibly in a single diffusion-controlled process.

POLAROGRAPHIC studies in thiosulphate solutions have been made for only a few metal ions¹⁻⁴. Davis¹ reported that two thiosulphate ions are bound to Pb(II) in 1 M thiosulphate solution. Vol'dman² determined the stability constants of three complexes of Pb(II) with $S_2O_3^{2-}$ in 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 metal to ligand ratio. The present study was undertaken to reinvestigate by polarography the coordination numbers and the formation constants of lead-thiosulphate complexes at different concentration of thiosulphate with varying ionic strength and ethanol content.

Experimental

A Radiometer PO4 polarograph was used for the study. The capillary characteristics were $m=2.16 \text{ mg sec}^{-1}$ and $t=4.1 \text{ sec}$ in 0.1 M KCl (open circuit) at a height of 55 cm Hg. Saturated calomel electrode was used as the reference electrode. Argon gas was used for the removal of dissolved oxygen. All measurements were done at 25°. The reagents employed were of A.R. grade. Sodium nitrate was used to adjust the ionic strength. Triton X-100 was used as maxima suppressor. The $E_{1/2}$ values were evaluated from the logarithmic analysis plots of the waves. A correction was made for the internal resistance drop.

Results and Discussion

The polarograms of 1 mM Pb(II), introduced as $Pb(NO_3)_2$, were recorded in solutions of different concentrations of thiosulphate (0.01 to 0.7 M) and at different ionic strengths ($\mu=0.15$ to 2.1). The ionic strength was adjusted by the addition of sodium nitrate and/or sodium thiosulphate. A maximum was observed in all the solutions which was suppressed by the addition of 0.1% Triton X-100.

A single wave was observed in the presence of sodium nitrate. On addition of sodium thiosulphate,

keeping the ionic strength constant, a shift in the half-wave potential towards more negative potential was observed. The shift is attributed to complex formation between Pb(II) and $S_2O_3^{2-}$. A slight decrease in the reduction current was also noticed due to the formation of bulky species which brings about a decrease in the diffusion coefficient.

The nature of the reduction wave was verified by the effect of mercury height on the limiting current. The $\log h$ vs $\log i$ plots were linear and having slopes amounting to 0.50-0.55 indicating that the reduction wave is diffusion controlled. On plotting the limiting currents vs different concentrations of Pb(II) (0.25 to 2.00 mM) at 0.1 M $Na_2S_2O_3$, a straight line passing through the origin was obtained confirming the validity of Ilkovic equation. The diffusion current constant was found as $6.70 \mu A/mM$.

The reversible polarographic reduction of Pb(II) in thiosulphate solution is proved by the logarithmic analysis plots of the wave. In each case the plot was a straight line whose slope (0.03) corresponded to the consumption of two electrons reversibly. Also, the values of $E_{1/2} - E_{3/2}$, which are equal to 0.0286 V, at different thiosulphate concentrations reveal the reversibility of the reduction process.

Composition and formation constants of the complexes

The coordination number of the complexes formed in solution by the interaction of Pb(II) ions and thiosulphate can be calculated by applying the following equation⁶

$$d(E_{1/2})_0^* / d \log [X] = \frac{0.059}{n} p$$

where n is the number of electrons involved in the reduction process, p is the coordination number, $(E_{1/2})_0^*$ is the half-wave potential of the complex corresponding to certain ligand concentration X .

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On plotting $(E_{1/2})_c$ vs $\log [X]$, straight lines are obtained at $\mu=0.15, 0.3, 0.6$ and 1.2 . The slopes of these lines are 0.06 at $\mu=0.15$ and $\mu=0.3$. However, at $\mu=0.6$ and 1.2 , a value of 0.09 of the slope is obtained. Substitution of the value of $0.059/n$ i.e., the slopes of the logarithmic analysis plots viz. 0.03 in the above equation, the values of p are found as 2 in the first case and 3 in the second case.

Another situation arises when the ionic strength is extended to 2.1 where the plot of $(E_{1/2})_c$ vs $\log [X]$ gives two linear sections intersected at $0.14 M$, as shown in Fig. 1. This indicates that two complexes are formed and their coordination numbers, as derived from the slopes of the linear sections, are 2 and 3 for the lower and the upper sections, respectively.

Fig. 1. $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [S_2O_3^{2-}]$ plot at $\mu = 2.1$

The $\Delta E_{1/2}$ values ($E_{1/2}$ complex- $E_{1/2}$ simple) were used to determine the overall formation constants for maximum coordination number, from the equation⁶,

$$\Delta E_{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{0.059}{2n} \log \frac{D_s}{D_o} - \frac{0.059}{n} \log \beta - p \frac{0.059}{n} \log [X]$$

The coordination numbers and the formation constants are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—COORDINATION NUMBERS AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF LEAD THIOSULPHATO COMPLEXES

$[S_2O_3^{2-}]$ <i>M</i>	μ	<i>p</i>	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_3$
0.01–0.05	0.15	2	5.33	—
0.02–0.10	0.30	2	5.00	—
0.04–0.20	0.60	3	—	5.63
0.08–0.40	1.20	3	—	5.26
0.03–0.14	2.10	2	3.90	—
0.14–0.70	2.10	3	—	5.17

From the data in Table 1, it is concluded that not only the concentration of $S_2O_3^{2-}$ but also the ionic strength exhibits a large effect on the stepwise formation of the complexes and their formation constant. A decrease in the formation constant is observed on increasing the ionic strength.

Effect of ethanol on the polarography of Pb(II) in thiosulphate solution :

A single wave was also observed for the reduction of 1 mM Pb(II) in thiosulphate solutions containing 10 to 50% ethyl alcohol at $\mu=0.15$. The half-wave potentials are shifted towards more negative potential and the current decreases on increasing the percentage of alcohol as can be seen from the representative data listed in Table 2. The effect of ethanol content was investigated in different concentration of $S_2O_3^{2-}$ (0.01 to $0.05 M$).

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF 1 mM Pb(II) IN $0.5 M S_2O_3^{2-}$ -ETHANOL MIXTURE

EtOH (v/v) %	<i>i</i> μA	$\frac{0.059}{n}$	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ V(SCE)	$E_{\frac{1}{2}} - E_{\frac{1}{2}}^0$ V	$D \times 10^6$ $cm^2 \cdot sec^{-1}$	$\log h$ vs slope
0	7.1	0.030	0.470	0.0286	7.63	0.50
10	6.2	0.030	0.478	0.0286	5.82	0.55
20	5.4	0.030	0.485	0.0286	4.41	0.55
30	4.6	0.031	0.500	0.0296	3.20	0.55
40	4.2	0.032	0.510	0.0300	2.67	0.55
50	4.2	0.033	0.535	0.0315	2.67	0.58

In all the experiments, the plots of $-E$ vs $\log i/i_a - i$ were found to be linear with the slope values lying in the 30 - 33 mV range which shows that the reduction of $Pb(II)$ ion in the presence of water-ethanol mixture is reversible and involves two electrons. The plots of $\log h$ vs $\log i$ proved that the reduction was diffusion controlled.

Variation of the percentage of alcohol brings about a large effect on the composition and the formation constant of the complexes. Thus, in the presence of 0 to 20% (v/v) ethanol, $p=2$ i.e. as in aqueous solution. In the presence of 30 and 40% ethanol two complexes with $p=2$ and 3 could be detected from the $(E_{1/2})_c$ vs $\log [X]$ plots. Finally, in the presence of 50% ethanol, the plot slope corresponded to the theoretical values for $p=3$. The data are given in Table 3. The formation constants of the complexes indicate that more stable complexes exist in water-ethanol mixtures due to solvation effects.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF ETHYL ALCOHOL CONTENT ON THE FORMATION CONSTANTS ($\mu = 0.15$)

Ethanol % (v/v)	$[S_2O_3^{2-}]$ <i>M</i>	<i>p</i>	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_3$
0.0	0.01–0.05	2	5.33	—
10.0	0.01–0.05	2	5.80	—
20.0	0.01–0.05	2	6.10	—
30.0	0.01–0.03	2	6.39	—
30.0	0.03–0.05	3	—	7.96
40.0	0.01–0.03	2	6.63	—
40.0	0.03–0.05	3	—	8.16
50.0	0.01–0.05	3	—	8.55

The present data indicate that there are conflicting views regarding the complexation of $S_2O_3^{2-}$ anion and Pb(II) ions. Davis¹, in his study on the polarography of metal thiosulphate complexes, found that only $Pb(S_2O_3)_2^{2-}$ is formed in 1 M $Na_2S_2O_3$ and the instability constant is 1.3×10^{-6} . According to the data obtained by Vol'dman⁵, the solubility product of PbS_2O_3 was calculated as 1.24×10^{-7} , and the stability constants of PbS_2O_3 , $Pb(S_2O_3)_2^{2-}$ and $Pb(S_2O_3)_3^{4-}$ are 2.26×10^5 , 4.35×10^5 and 7.19×10^6 , respectively.

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